

ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS AMONG THE POPULATION, EDUCATION AND TRAINING FOR THE PRESENTATION MADANIYAT EXPLAIN.

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Annotatsiya: This article describes the population among environmental education, environmental education, environmental awareness, ecological culture, “Environmental education in the development of irish concept”, the age of the environmental literacy to increase, environmental problems and them prevent to get, environmental education and education improvement about the information given.

Key words: population of the environmental literacy to increase, the ecolumn education, environmental education, ecology, ecological culture, gumumbashariy problems, environmental awareness, environmental education, natural environment, environmental knowledge.

In the republic the population among environmental consciousness and culture development and environmental education education promote to, the young generation of environmental literacy of the consolidation on the concept of working out and to the problem the solution to find the most necessary is. The republic in the territory of the environmental problems, the solution to the education system, the current make with contribute added to the growth of the coming age avlydda its ecology with sync to grow , to increase, environmental awareness and ecological culture shakllantirish and development, environmental education and training process effective tashcellar to order 2019-year, 27-may “the uzbekistan republic in Environmental educationi the development of on VQ-434-dated 2019 is the year of 30 October “by 2030 and make the year of theacha to the period of Uzbekistan republic of the Surrounding environment protection toh on” UP-5863-dated Concept and other normative-legal documents belgilab was put. This decision according to continuous education in the system of ecological units’of education in the development of the main principles set, them educational process consistency with step-by-step implementation of to and the same on the basis of environmental education new level of lifting; Education programs existing environmental problems and themto , eliminating the task come out improvement; Education the recipient of the attention of the humany environmental problems to focus through their mother to the nature of re - recoveryan source store stay in and of them rational use in the field mas’umliyat of enhancing; Environmental education effective forms and methods of work out and the current to; and environmental education, quality, personnel training system of the effectivegini and sustainable development guarantees and priority is providing normativ-legal, material-technical and information base to create; Ecology and around thdog protection to field competent state authorities and the education sectorg mutually beneficial cooperation in the development directed tasks, the number ish out boosts are.

The decision of environmental problems of global importance about have the fact that considering and get around environment protection, ecological culture and environmental education, education, environmental education issues of particular attention are given. Education systemg all stages, environmental awareness, environmental education, ecological culture, globall environmental problems eliminate to, the natural environment back restore to nationwide events conduct will be implied. Pre-school education organizations and general secondary education schools, secondary special, professional education system, higher education system, higher education next education system, Personnel training and skills enhancement on the stage ofthe world's ecological education in the system of improving, school in addition to ta'education in the system of environmental education improving systematic set is implied. The ecolun education development from the concept of expected results; environmental education tarbiya process of systematic organization to, young people among environmental knowledge and culture tarbrick making, environmental sox advanced innovative technologies involved in was without againthough improving, young people, Mother nature is love and his eyes qorachiqek to preserve aims knowledge and skills increase to the methods of the basis isb service makes. The concept of made that can be our country, the nature of the, ecosystem, around the environment stability in the ride to keep serve the will and the population of all qatlam of ecological culture, the enhancement of contributing to it will add. "The population of ecological culture is increasing about the serious home secure we need" — Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the republic of February 2, on waste with the work system improvement and the area of the ecological position improve, "Green space" of the national project implementation increasing on a year by 2022 - priority tasks facefrom asi videoselektor at the meeting all of you better know, our people from the beginning nature is holy that you know. Soil, water, air, ostonadan of pure to keep has been striving. Our nation "Birni his cut, the ten ek" that 's a wise saying is also avail I could not.In the family new child into the world came, him called germination planted. Unfortunately, this same good habits today almost lost went. Today the world on the scale of engineering and technology, industry, high level of developed XXI century ecology with associated problems in the first level of the problem as the day of order is no accident that it is not. We of this matter and only the future is not, near , and far in the future, think of working if you keep it, sure our goals to achieve , we are unable", — says thestate of the head. Our generation , we then also likely natural environment live to our nature, kindness and attention that we may giveit with in harmony to be live we should. Is this what you mean? This is - nature - clean-tidy to keep, land and water resources, ecological systems, preservation, tree planting, garden to create the mean. The most important issues of the population, ecological culture, increasing about serious home secure we needed. Today the street or any place to see. All in place of people away gone to waste , you see. We native land, our holy I call. You the same country in the same soil us for holy is, what for it clean and tidy we do not keep? Of course, such problems only administrative way with solved are not. Thus, the young generation at the heart of mother nature, in love, her affected with a sense of nurturing by achieve can. In the neighborhood, in the street waste who remove the man when he saw, "this your work wrong is", who can say the environment in the form of, our people it teach that we need. This is us all our work and personal duty".

Ecology itself is what? Ecology the word eshtishimiz with eyes before us the street clean to keep, water protection to, yes, the von pollution kept does not come. Ecology – present the

times of wide scale dramatically to social problems is one. Environmental problems, to the solution of all the people to the interests of suited is, the civilization of the present day, and the future is in many respects in this problem the solution is related. Ecology- of-life process balmof n, man's environment is a problem of their own distinctive style of research doigan independent fandır. Ecologiya "Natural home" to learn, differently do Igan in the ecology of the organism "residence place" of science if it is, then the main focus of the body, the interaction and external environment between the links character to focus on. Today's day in society, into the consciousness of environmental culture absorption necessary, environmental consciousness, environmental education and education for human life, lifestyle and manaviyatini change needed. Environmental education related to the concept of social from the side the lower, as explained can be. Environmental educationm - environmental education itself is what? Environmental education – the man to life, jumladan to work to prepare tizimlash was, term, formal, appropriate environmental bscience, skills and qualifications to give means. Environmental education – the man of high ecological spiritualwith iyat , and the enlightenment of the individual of the preparation tool. Nature with a constant muloqotda to be man's moral rivoyajlanishining necessary condition.

Markus topic on get to go in searchof h results from such a conclusion to make it possible: in nature all the changesng motivator man , it's so, the ecological look many times to your country primarily ourselves we needed the fact that it's incredibly important, when the "Bird 's nest see that you will" so that for the environmental surroundings, the environment, the protection of the modern environment and its improvement, preserve jealously to also meaningthat the ul training sessions in modern environmental education based without settingsvojlantirish should be. This growth coming future generations to environmental consciousness and culture at the form ofantirish also important is professional is.

References:

1. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev waste with again to work the system and environmental position to improve, "Green space" of the national project implementation increase in the field videoselektor the assemblies of speech
<https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4955>
2. H. t. Tursunov, T,He,Rakhimova ecology study guide "Maple en" we have environmental publishing company Tashkent-2006 (12-15bet)
3. Ecology of Uzbekistan republic of the Higher and secondary special education of the ministry of textbooks
Dilorom in yormatov (14-20bet) Tashkent-2012.
4. The uzbekistan republic in Environmental education, the development of the concept of approval on 2019-year, 27-may 434-number resolution <https://lex.uz/docs/>
5. Uzbekistan respublika of daekologik education development corporationpsiyasini approval on
<https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-4354743>